

Assessment Of Quality of Life and Clinical Outcomes in Type 2 Diabetes: A Comparative Study of Metformin-Based Combination Therapies Using SF-12

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the quality of life of diabetes patients receiving various combination therapies. This cross-sectional study included 212 T2D patients aged 18–80 years, receiving treatment for at least six months. The quality of life was evaluated using SF-12 questionnaire which was asked during OP patient counselling session. SPSS statistical software was used to examine the data. According to statistics, the correlation for all the variables pair are negative and statistically, it indicates the lower QoL score. The strongest association is between HbA1c & physical QoL indicating that physical health is most affected if there is a poor glucose/ glycemic control. The combination of metformin + SGLT2 inhibitors shows the best clinical effectiveness against the glycemic control, whereas DPP-4 inhibitor + thiazolidinedione show intermediate control followed by metformin + sulphonylurea combination. Metformin plus SGLT-2 inhibitor combinations represent the optimal choice for type 2 diabetes management across multiple outcome domains. The combination achieved superior glycemic control, showed the least amount of hypoglycemia and the best safety profile and weight gain, and consistently produced the greatest quality of life ratings in every area examined. Similarly, the substantial inverse correlation between BMI and quality of life supports preferential use of weight-neutral or weight-reducing medications like SGLT-2 inhibitors.

Keywords: Quality of life, Type 2 diabetes mellitus, SF 12 form, Oral hypoglycemic agents, combination therapy.

INTRODUCTION

The management of Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is influenced by clinical practice guidelines, institutional protocols, and physician judgment, which are further shaped by patient satisfaction, safety, efficacy, and tolerability. Adherence to clinical guidelines is essential to improve treatment standards and healthcare outcomes [6]. Diabetes management requires lifestyle modifications such as dietary regulation, regular exercise, medication adherence, and glucose monitoring, which can burden patients and families, thereby reducing quality of life (QoL). The WHO defines QoL as an The approach with which an individual views their place in life in relation to cultural context, goals, and expectations, and it is now recognized as a key health outcome. Diabetes substantially impairs health-related quality of life (HRQoL), especially in the presence of comorbidities.

The American Diabetes Association recommends a “patient-centered” approach, prioritizing glycemic control, complication prevention, and QoL improvement [1].

Several factors influence QoL in diabetes, including demographic (age, gender, marital status, socioeconomic and educational status), clinical (duration of illness, insulin use, complications, HbA1C, comorbidities, BMI), and psychosocial variables (depression, support systems, and disease awareness) [1]. Reliable QoL measurement requires multidimensional assessment across cultural boundaries [2]. Domains such as functional, physical, psychological, and social health are necessary to capture diverse aspects, as QoL evaluation can guide prognosis, therapy effectiveness, and patient perspectives [3]. Depression and poor QoL reduce treatment adherence, and most Tools for QoL have

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been created in Western populations, limiting applicability to Indian settings [4]. The SF-12 questionnaire, a shorter validated version of SF-36, is widely used in both general and disease-specific populations. It covers eight health domains role limits (physical and emotional), physical functioning, vitality, social functioning, and mental health, body pain, and general health using 12 items with acute and standard recall options [5]. Cost-effective and rational prescribing in diabetes improves compliance, reduces dropouts, minimizes complications, and enhances QoL [9]. Diabetes imposes a high financial burden, including direct healthcare costs, productivity losses, and intangible psychological costs [7, 8]. Prevention and Therefore, education is essential for both patients and others in the community, alongside rational drug use. According to WHO, rational prescribing involves providing appropriate medications at the correct dose, duration, and lowest cost. Drug use studies offer evidence to evaluate prescription trends, adverse reactions, and rising treatment costs. To support rational prescribing, the WHO has introduced core drug-use indicators addressing prescribing, patient care, and facility practices [9].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study setting

The Department of General Medicine at a Teaching and General Hospital in Hyderabad, India, was the site of a hospital-based study. The study recruited patients from the outpatient department who had been diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus for at least six months prior to the trial.

Study criteria:

Inclusion

Patients with Type-II Diabetes Mellitus, aged between 18 and 80 years, who had been receiving

Oral hypoglycaemic agents (OHA) for a minimum duration of three months. Additionally included were patients receiving OHA in combination therapy.

Exclusion

Patients unwilling to participate, individuals with notable comorbidities, including cancer, and individuals with alcoholism or manic disorders were not included in the research.

Sampling Method:

Patients attending the outpatient department (OPD) who got to know the eligibility criteria were selected and allocated into different drug-combination groups. The study procedure was explained to each patient, and written informed consent was acquired prior to enrolment.

Questionnaire:

Health-related The quality of life has been assessed using the standardized health Effects Study SF-12 questionnaire. Eight domains are assessed by this tool: mental health, role emotional, social functioning, physical functioning, role physical, bodily pain, vitality, and general health. Scores range from 0 (indicating the worst possible status) to 100 (indicating the best possible status), except for the pain domain, where a higher score reflects greater pain. Diabetes status was self-reported with the following options: (1) Yes, but not on medication, (2) Yes, on oral anti-diabetic medication (excluding insulin), (3) Yes, on insulin, or a combination of options (2) and (3) for patients on both therapies.

Follow-up:

Every patient that was enrolled had already received structured diabetes education during earlier visits, with an average duration of three to six months.

Steps in scoring of PCS and MCS:

Step 1: Data Cleaning and Item Recoding

All 12 items are checked for out-of-range values, which are set to missing. Four items (GH1, BP2, MH3, VT2) are reverse scored such that better health is constantly reflected in higher values.

Step 2: Creating Indicator Variable for Item Response Choices

Indicator (dummy) Variables are established for every response category, with the exception of the best health state. Out of 47 response choices, 35 indicator variables are generated.

Step 3: Weighting and Aggregation of Indicator Variables

Each indicator variable is multiplied by its respective regression weight (physical or mental) and summed to

produce PCS-12 and MCS-12 scores. If any item is missing, the summary score is set to missing.

Step 4: Norm-Based Standardization of Scale Scores

Scores are standardized to the U.S. population norms, giving PCS-12 and MCS-12 50 as the mean and 10 as the standard deviation (“50/10 scoring”).

Scoring Checks

Ensure no out-of-range values and indicator variables coded only as 0 or 1. Physical functioning, role physical, and bodily pain should correlate more with PCS-12, while There should be a stronger correlation between MCS-12 and social functioning, role-emotion, and mental health.

GH1 usually relates more to PCS-12 and VT2 to MCS-12. Correlation between PCS-12 and MCS-12 should remain low; deviations may signal scoring errors.

RESULTS

A total of 220 patients were approached and out of them 8 subjects discontinued. Thus, the final sample size was 212. The collected data were analyzed to assess the demographic distribution across different therapy types. In the population under investigation, where demographic were assessed it shows male predominance, whereas in case of comparison of hypertension and dyslipidemia as the impact of clinical variables, HTN outnumber the dyslipidemia. [Table 1]

TABLE.1: Influence of Demographic/Clinical Factors

Variable	Category	Percentage
Gender	Male	55%
Gender	Female	45%
Co morbidities	Hypertension	60%
Co morbidities	Dyslipidemia	42%

The improved glycemic management attained with metformin plus SGLT-2 inhibitor combination (HbA1c 7.2%) compared to metformin plus sulfonylurea (7.8%) and DPP-4 inhibitor plus thiazolidinedione (7.5%) reflects established clinical evidence supporting SGLT-2 inhibitors as preferred

second-line agents. The combination of metformin + SGLT2 inhibitors shows the best clinical effectiveness against the glycemic control, whereas DPP-4 inhibitor + thiazolidinedione show intermediate control followed by metformin + sulphonylurea combination. [Table 2]

TABLE.2: Clinical Effectiveness of Drug Combinations

Drug Combination	HbA1c (%)	FBS (mg/dL)	PPBS (mg/dL)
Metformin + Sulfonylurea	7.8	152.3	204.6
Metformin + SGLT-2 Inhibitor	7.2	143.8	190.5
DPP-4 Inhibitor + Thiazolidinedione	7.5	148.1	198.4

The safety analysis revealed the highest hypoglycemia risk with metformin plus sulfonylurea (20%), compared to SGLT-2 inhibitor (6.7%) and DPP-4 plus thiazolidinedione (3.3%) combinations, confirming established sulfonylurea safety concerns. Additionally, weight increase was more common with sulfonylurea therapy (16.7%) versus SGLT-2 inhibitor regimens (3.3%). The DPP-4 plus TZD

combination demonstrated the most advantageous safety profile with negligible adverse events.

While metformin plus SGLT-2 inhibitors showed good safety with only a small incidence of renal complications. Overall, metformin plus sulfonylurea exhibited the least favorable safety profile due to

higher rates of hypoglycemia, GI disturbances, and weight gain.

Safety Profile: DPP 4i + TZD > Met +SGLT2i > Met +SU. [Graph 1]

The consistent superiority of metformin plus SGLT-2 inhibitor combinations across all quality of life domains (physical: 65.7, mental: 66.2, social: 67.1, functional: 68.3) compared to other combinations provides compelling evidence for patient-centered treatment selection. This finding is particularly significant given the strong relationship between medication burden and quality of life demonstrated by

the progressive decline in total QoL ratings when the number of drugs increases (1 drug: 62.1±7.8; 2 drugs: 58.3±8.5; ≥3 drugs: 53.7±9.2). The combination of Met + SGLT2i shows the highest score in all the QoL domains followed by DPP4i+TZD with intermediate scoring. Met+SU got the lowest score across all the QoL domains. [Graph 2]

The correlation for all the variables pair are negative and statistically, it indicates the lower QoL score. The strongest association is between HbA1c & physical QoL (r = -0.41) indicating that physical health is most

affected if there is a poor glucose/ glycemic control. [Table 5]

TABLE 3: Correlation Between Glycemic Control and QoL

Variable Pair	Correlation (r)	p-value
HbA1c vs. Physical QoL	-0.41	0.004
FBS vs. Functional QoL	-0.38	0.006
HbA1c vs. Mental QoL	-0.35	0.01
RBS vs. Social QoL	-0.3	0.015

This analysis reveals the inverse relationship between and physical & mental health that is as the BMI increases the QoL decreases.

The population with normal BMI (18-24) exhibit highest QoL score as the BMI increases that is ≥ 30 In the event of an obese population, In terms of both mental and physical health, quality of life declines. [Graph 3]

When the relationship between the duration and HbA1c was assessed it reveals the direct proportionally.

The HbA1c value rises with the length of time a person has diabetes, indicating poor glycemic control over time.

This comparison reveals the positive association between duration and HbA1c. [Graph 4]

The patient on monotherapy, dual therapy and polytherapy are assessed for quality of life, it shows that monotherapy reports higher QoL.

This parameter exhibits inverse relationship between number of drugs & QoL. [Graph 5]

The data of 212 diabetic patients, out of which 118 are males & 94 are females were analysed for the QoL, it shows males have slightly better QoL for both mental and Physical health.

Males also have a marginally higher mean overall quality of life than females. [Table 4]

TABLE.4: QoL by Gender

Gender	n	Mean Physical QoL	Mean Mental QoL	Mean Total QoL
Male	118	57.8	56.2	57
Female	94	54.6	52.9	53.8

Table.5 : ANOVA / Correlation FOR QOL RESULTS

Test	F / r	p-value	Interpretation
ANOVA	9.45	<0.001*	Significant (p < 0.001)
Pearson Correlation (r)	-0.38	<0.001*	Negative correlation (more drugs = lower QoL)

Table.6: Independent t-Test

QoL Domain	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Physical Well-being	2.94	0.004*	Significant (p < 0.05)
Mental Well-being	2.67	0.009*	Significant (p < 0.05)
Total QoL Score	2.81	0.006*	Significant (p < 0.05)

Table.7: ANOVA for BMI vs. QoL

QoL Domain	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Physical Well-being	6.84	0.002*	Significant difference (p < 0.05)
Mental Well-being	5.12	0.008*	Significant difference (p < 0.05)

DISCUSSION

Clinical Effectiveness and Glycemic Control

This study demonstrated the superiority of metformin plus SGLT-2 inhibitor combinations across multiple outcome domains, consistent with evidence supporting early combination therapy for optimal outcomes [10, 11]. A clinically meaningful 0.6% difference in HbA1c was noted between the best and worst performing regimens, with even modest HbA1c reductions translating into significant long-term cardiovascular and microvascular risk reduction [12–14]. The correlation between HbA1c and QoL (physical: $r = -0.41$; mental: $r = -0.35$, $p = 0.01$) highlights the close link between glycemic control and patient well-being.

Safety Profile Considerations

Safety profiles varied across drug combinations, underscoring the need for individualized therapy [10, 15, 16]. The lower risk of hypoglycemia and weight gain with SGLT-2 inhibitor regimens likely contributed to superior QoL scores, enhancing adherence and treatment satisfaction [17–19].

Results of Quality of Life and the expenditure of Treatment

A negative correlation between medication burden and QoL ($r = -0.38$, $p < 0.001$) emphasizes the benefit of simplified regimens. Fixed-dose or lower pill-burden combinations, such as SGLT-2 inhibitor-based therapies, may optimize both clinical outcomes and QoL [17, 18, 20].

Demographic and Clinical Factors

Gender-based QoL differences (males: 57.0 vs. females: 53.8) reflect established disparities in diabetes outcomes [15, 20, 21]. BMI-stratified data showed Patients who were obese had much lower physical (52.1 ± 10.6) and mental (50.8 ± 9.7) QoL scores, reinforcing the value of weight-neutral or weight-reducing therapies like SGLT-2 inhibitors [16, 23, 24].

Activity Limitation and Functional Outcomes

Progressive improvement in functional capacity was evident, with severe limitation declining from 19.8% to 7.8% and no limitation rising from 12.3% to 18.0% across visits. These improvements ($\chi^2 = 15.72$, $p = 0.003$) confirm that structured diabetes management

enhances physical independence and daily functioning [25, 26].

Treatment Adherence and Long-term Outcomes

Better glycemic control was linked to better adherence, fewer complications, and higher QoL [20, 27, 28]. The superior outcomes of SGLT-2 inhibitor combinations likely reflect both clinical efficacy and adherence advantages due to favourable tolerability and once-daily dosing [29, 30]. Sustained adherence remains essential for long-term complication prevention and QoL maintenance.

CONCLUSION

This thorough research shows that the best option for managing type 2 diabetes across a number of outcome areas is a combination of metformin and SGLT-2 inhibitors. The combination consistently produced the best quality of life scores across all domains tested, demonstrated the most favorable safety profile with little weight gain (3.3%) and hypoglycemia (6.7%), and achieved improved glycemic control (HbA1c 7.2%). Since the observed differences in quality of life outcomes between men and women may reflect different treatment responses necessitating individualized therapeutic approaches, gender-specific considerations should guide treatment selection. Similarly, preferential use of weight-neutral or weight-reducing drugs, such as SGLT-2 inhibitors, is supported by the significant inverse association between BMI and quality of life.

The temporal improvement in functional outcomes observed across study visits demonstrates that the most effective therapy for diabetes can reverse activity limitations and improve patients' physical capabilities over time. **Clinical implications** include the recommendation for earlier initiation of SGLT-2 inhibitor-based combinations, particularly in patients with higher BMI or quality of life concerns. The superior benefit-risk profile of these combinations, combined with their positive impact on cardiovascular and renal outcomes established in large clinical trials, supports their position as preferred second-line therapy after metformin. **Future research** should focus on developing personalized treatment algorithms that incorporate quality of life assessments alongside traditional clinical parameters. Long-term studies examining the

durability of these benefits and cost-effectiveness analyses considering both clinical outcomes and quality of life improvements would further inform evidence-based diabetes care practices.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study was approved by Institutional ethical committee of Shadan Institute of Medical Sciences Teaching Hospital and Research Centre, Hyderabad, Telangana. With Ref no: 069/SIMS/Research/2023.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

We declare no conflict of interest

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